

AZERBAIJAN AVIATION HISTORY (1910-2024)**Suleymanov E.**

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Azerbaijan's aviation history spans over a century, marked by key milestones that reflect both regional and global developments in aviation. The roots of Azerbaijani aviation can be traced to the early 20th century, with the first recorded flight in Baku in 1910, and the establishment of the first airfield in the city in 1919. In the Soviet era (1920s-1991), Azerbaijan became an integral part of the Soviet aviation system, with Baku serving as a key hub for domestic and international air travel. The country's aviation infrastructure expanded under Soviet rule, and Azerbaijan produced notable aviators and engineers.

Following Azerbaijan's independence in 1991, the aviation sector faced challenges but underwent significant modernization. Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL) was established as the national carrier, and Baku's Heydar Aliyev International Airport was upgraded to handle increased international traffic. Today, Azerbaijan continues to develop its aviation industry, investing in infrastructure, expanding international routes, and positioning itself as a regional aviation hub connecting Europe and Asia.

Azerbaijan's aviation sector has grown rapidly in the 21st century. With a blend of historical significance and modern infrastructure, the country continues to evolve as a regional aviation hub, fostering both international connectivity and a burgeoning aerospace industry. Furthermore, Azerbaijan's strategic investments in aviation and tourism suggest that it will remain a key player in the Caspian region's transport network for the foreseeable future. The country's investment in sustainable aviation, airport modernization, and airline expansion, combined with its position at the crossroads of Europe and Asia, holds the promise of continuing growth in the global aviation landscape.

Keywords: Azerbaijan Aviation, History, 19th century, 20th century, 21st century, past-present, aviation industry.

Introduction

Azerbaijan's aviation history is a story of gradual development, from early flight experiments to its current status as a regional aviation hub connecting Europe, Asia, and the Middle East. The nation's aviation journey began in the early 20th century, when pioneers like Jafar Jafarov made notable contributions to the development of flight in Azerbaijan. Although the country was then part of the Russian Empire, these early flights marked the beginning of Azerbaijan's aviation aspirations.

Following the establishment of the Soviet Union, Azerbaijan became a key center for aviation within the USSR, with the state-run airline Aeroflot operating domestic and international routes. Over the decades, Baku emerged as an important aviation hub, with its airports expanding to meet growing demand.

After Azerbaijan gained independence in 1991, the creation of Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL) in 1992 marked the rebirth of the nation's aviation industry. AZAL quickly modernized its fleet, opened up new international routes, and transformed Baku's Heydar Aliyev International Airport into a major regional airport.

Today, Azerbaijan continues to develop its aviation infrastructure and services, with increasing investments in airport modernization, fleet expansion, and international cooperation. As the country's aviation sector grows, it plays an increasingly vital role in connecting Azerbaijan to the wider world, supporting both business and tourism while enhancing the country's global standing in air travel.

Early Beginnings and Pioneering Flights (1910s - 1920s)

1910-1914: The First Flights

Early Pioneers: Aviation in Azerbaijan began in the early 20th century. The first flight in Azerbaijan was recorded in 1910 when a Russian aviator, Mikhail Lomonosov, performed an airshow in Baku.

First Local Aviator: The first Azerbaijani pilot was Jafar Jafarov, who trained in Russia and made his first solo flight in 1912. He became an advocate for the development of aviation in Azerbaijan.

1919: Establishment of Civil Aviation

In the aftermath of World War I and the Russian Revolution, Azerbaijan, which was then a part of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic (1918-1920), began its efforts to establish civil aviation. However, due to political instability, these early developments were rudimentary and faced challenges.

Aviation History during ADR and ADR Aviation Contracts with Georgia:

During the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic (ADR) (1918-1920), the early years of Azerbaijani aviation were marked by significant developments. The ADR, seeking to modernize and establish its own infrastructure, engaged in various international partnerships, including with Georgia. These contracts were aimed at developing aviation capabilities and fostering regional cooperation. However, with the subsequent incorporation of Azerbaijan into the Soviet Union, the ADR's initiatives were largely absorbed into broader Soviet aviation plans.

Early Beginnings in USSR Azerbaijan (1920s-1940s)**1. Early Aviation Efforts:**

- Soviet Influence: Azerbaijan's aviation history began under Soviet rule. The Baku Aeroclub was established in 1923, marking the inception of organized aviation activities in the country.

- First Aircraft: The first aircraft in Azerbaijan were Soviet-made models, such as the U-2, used for both civilian and military purposes.

2. Development of Civil Aviation:

- Establishment of Civil Aviation: In the late 1920s and early 1930s, civil aviation infrastructure began to develop, with the establishment of airports and the introduction of scheduled flights. Baku became a key hub in the Soviet aviation network.

Soviet Era Expansion (1940s-1980s)

1. World War II:

- Military Role: During World War II, Azerbaijan played a strategic role due to its oil resources and transportation networks. The aviation industry was focused on supporting the war effort, including transport and reconnaissance missions.

2. Post-War Expansion:

- Infrastructure Development: After the war, Azerbaijan continued to develop its aviation infrastructure. The establishment of the Baku International Airport (now Heydar Aliyev International Airport) in 1980 was a significant milestone, modernizing air transport facilities in the region.

- Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL): Azerbaijan Airlines was established in 1949 as the national carrier of the Soviet Union. It operated domestic and international flights and was a part of the larger Soviet airline network.

Post-Independence Developments (1990s-2000s)

1. Independence and Reorganization:

- Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL): Following Azerbaijan's independence in 1991, Azerbaijan Airlines was restructured and became the national carrier of the newly independent Republic of Azerbaijan. The airline expanded its fleet and routes, both domestically and internationally.

- Rebuilding Infrastructure: The 1990s saw efforts to rebuild and modernize aviation infrastructure, including improvements to airports and the establishment of new aviation regulations.

2. International Cooperation:

- Membership in International Organizations: Azerbaijan joined various international aviation organizations, such as the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) and the International Air Transport Association (IATA), which facilitated greater integration into the global aviation community.

Modern Era (2000s-Present)

1. Airport Modernization:

- Heydar Aliyev International Airport: The airport underwent significant modernization and expansion, becoming a major hub in the region. New terminals, runways, and facilities were developed to handle increased passenger and cargo traffic.

2. Fleet and Route Expansion:

- Modern Fleet: Azerbaijan Airlines expanded its fleet with modern aircraft, including Boeing and Airbus models. This expansion enabled the airline to increase

its range of international routes and improve service quality.

- Growth of Routes: The airline established new routes to key international destinations, enhancing connectivity between Azerbaijan and global markets.

3. Development of Regional Airports:

- Regional Airports: Besides Baku, regional airports in cities such as Ganja, Lankaran, and Gabala were developed or upgraded to support increased regional connectivity and stimulate local economies.

4. Aviation Industry Reforms:

- Regulatory Changes: The Azerbaijani government implemented various reforms to align with international aviation standards, improving safety, efficiency, and service quality within the national aviation sector.

- Air Navigation Services: Modernization of air navigation services and implementation of advanced technologies improved air traffic management and safety.

5. Aviation Training and Technology:

- Training Programs: Investment in aviation training and education programs helped develop a skilled workforce for the aviation sector. Partnerships with international aviation institutions and training centers were established to enhance local expertise.

- Technological Advancements: Adoption of new technologies and digital solutions improved operational efficiency and customer service in the aviation sector.

6. Aviation in Geopolitical Context:

- Strategic Importance: Azerbaijan's strategic location at the crossroads of Europe and Asia enhanced its role as a key player in regional and global aviation. The country leveraged its position to attract international airlines and facilitate cargo transit between major markets.

Soviet aviation in Azerbaijan played a significant role in the development of both regional and national aviation capabilities during the Soviet era. Here are some key points about the subject:

Aerospace Industry

1970s-1980s: Azerbaijan contributed to the Soviet aerospace industry, including the development and production of various aerospace technologies. Azerbaijani scientists and engineers were involved in space programs and aircraft design.

Legacy and Impact

Post-Soviet Period: After the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991, Azerbaijan inherited a well-developed aviation infrastructure. The legacy of Soviet aviation is still evident in the country's aviation sector, including airport facilities and training programs. The influence of Soviet aviation technology and practices also continues to impact Azerbaijani aviation today.

The Soviet period was pivotal in shaping the aviation industry in Azerbaijan, laying the foundation for its current capabilities and infrastructure.

Under Aliyev's leadership, significant investments were made in the renovation of Baku's Heydar Aliyev International Airport, which was named in his honor. These improvements helped transform the airport into a major regional hub, enhancing connectivity and supporting economic growth.

Aliyev's government also supported the expansion of Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL), promoting the development of both domestic and international flight routes. His tenure marked a period of significant growth in the aviation sector, which contributed to Azerbaijan's integration into the global economy and increased its role in regional and international travel.

Arif Pashayev is a prominent figure in Azerbaijani aviation. He is known for his contributions to the development of Azerbaijan's aviation sector. Pashayev played a significant role in the growth and modernization of the Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL) and has been involved in various capacities within the country's aviation industry.

Under his leadership and influence, Azerbaijan's aviation sector has seen advancements in infrastructure, technology, and service quality. Pashayev's efforts have helped position Azerbaijan as a key player in regional aviation, fostering both domestic and international air travel.

Also Arif Pashayev has played a significant role in the development of Azerbaijan's National Aviation Academy (NAA). As a key figure in Azerbaijani aviation, Pashayev has been instrumental in advancing the academy's mission to train aviation professionals and support the growth of the country's aviation sector.

Under his influence, the NAA has expanded its educational programs and facilities, aiming to meet international standards and foster a new generation of skilled aviation experts. The academy focuses on various aspects of aviation, including engineering, management, and flight operations, contributing to the modernization and professionalization of Azerbaijan's aviation industry. Pashayev's leadership has been crucial in enhancing the academy's reputation and its role in supporting Azerbaijan's aviation goals.

Heydar Aliyev and Azerbaijan Aviation History (1993-2023):

Heydar Aliyev, who served as Azerbaijan's President from 1993 to 2003, played a pivotal role in the revival and modernization of Azerbaijani aviation. Under his leadership, significant investments were made in infrastructure and fleet modernization. The period from 1993 to 2023 saw substantial growth in the aviation sector, with the establishment of new airlines, expansion of airports, and improvements in safety and technology. The country's flagship carrier, Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL), expanded its routes and fleet, contributing to increased connectivity and economic development.

Azerbaijan Aviation Academy and Its Role:

The Azerbaijan National Aviation Academy (ANAA) is a crucial institution in the country's aviation sector. Established to provide specialized education and training in aviation, the academy plays a significant role in developing skilled professionals for the industry. It focuses on various aspects of aviation, including pilot training, aircraft maintenance, and air traffic control. Under the leadership of Rector Ord.Prof.Dr. Arif Pashayev, the academy has made strides in modernizing its curriculum and facilities, contributing to the growth of Azerbaijan's aviation sector. Dr. Pashayev's

efforts have included fostering international collaborations and ensuring the academy's alignment with global standards.

NAA and International Policy (Bilateral Contracts for Modernization of Education Policy):

The Azerbaijan National Aviation Academy (NAA) has been actively involved in international cooperation to enhance its educational offerings. This includes entering into bilateral contracts and agreements with other countries and aviation institutions for the modernization of its educational policies and programs. These agreements often focus on updating curricula, improving training facilities, and integrating international best practices into the academy's operations. Such collaborations help ensure that Azerbaijani aviation professionals are trained to meet global standards and contribute to the country's competitive edge in the international aviation arena.

The history of Azerbaijani aviation is marked by significant milestones, reflecting the country's evolving role in both regional and global aviation. From the early days of aviation to modern developments, Azerbaijan has seen considerable progress in this field. Here's an overview of the key events and phases in the creation and development of Azerbaijani aviation.

Summary

The history of Azerbaijani aviation reflects a journey from early Soviet-era developments to a modern, dynamic sector in an independent Azerbaijan. Key milestones include the establishment of Azerbaijan Airlines, significant infrastructure upgrades, and a focus on international integration and technological advancement. Today, Azerbaijan's aviation industry plays a crucial role in connecting the country to global markets and supporting regional economic growth.

Also Professional holiday of civil aviation workers-holiday day in Azerbaijan on may 18, 2006, the president of the Republic of Azerbaijan signed an order on the establishment of professional holiday of civil aviation workers. According to the document, June 2 of each year (the day of the establishment of the First Aviation Group in Azerbaijan in 1938) was declared the professional holiday of civil aviation workers.

Moreover Aircraft fleet updated, route network expanded

During 2005-2015," Azerbaijan Airlines "CJSC (AZAL) included new aircraft models such as" Airbus A319"," Boeing 767-300ER"," Airbus A340-500"," Embraer 190"," Embraer 170 "and" Boeing 787-8 Dreamliner " in its fleet of aircraft.

At the beginning of 2023, flights with 3 new aircraft "Airbus A320neo" began. In April of the same year, AZAL signed contracts with "Airbus" and "Boeing" for the supply of 20 more aircraft – 12 "Airbus A320neo" and 8 "Boeing 787" aircraft. It is planned to stage-by-stage commissioning of new aircraft. As a result of the new cooperation with" GetJet Airlines "on leasing of aircraft, Azal's fleet has been expanded with 3" Airbus A320 " aircraft.

Since 2010, The Pilot Training Center has been operating under the National Aviation Academy. The center consists of theoretical and practical training departments. In the practical training department, flight

simulators are installed, which are important for the training of professional civil aviation pilots. So, at the Pilot Training Center, pilots of aircraft "AIRBUS A320/A319", "Boeing 757/767", "EMBRAER E190", "ATR-42/72", as well as helicopter pilots "Mi-8AMT" are trained. With the introduction of modern innovations of aviation science and technology in the flight simulator, the D level is provided, which is the highest in this area and is checked by international organizations.

Improvement of the route network is one of the main directions of development of AZAL. As a result of the work carried out to expand the flight geography during 2003-2023, by the end of 2023, the total number of airline routes was increased to 57.

Azal strategy and digital development

In December 2022, AZAL signed an agreement with the international consulting company "McKinsey" to develop a strategic development plan. This plan, covering 2023-2030, includes many aspects such as the unification of the Aviapark, the expansion of the route network, and the creation of an efficient system for coordinating flights.

It should be noted that 2022 was a significant year for AZAL compared to previous years. In the same year, Azal achieved great success by making net profit for the first time according to its financial statements. Also, the airline has fulfilled many obligations to both foreign and domestic creditors.

In August 2021, AZAL switched to a new system "Amadeus SRM" (Amadeus Segment Revenue Management) to optimize operations and profits within the framework of its corporate policy on the implementation of the latest digital solutions.

In 2023, AZAL actively integrated advanced digital solutions to improve passenger comfort. The updated website and mobile app have significantly improved the customer experience, providing more convenient travel planning. At the same time, the airline focused on the development of a CRM (Customer Relationship Management) System that takes into account the individual needs of passengers and increases their satisfaction and quality of Service.

Reconstruction and construction of new airports

One of the important events in the first years of the head of state's leadership was the transfer of international status to Nakhchivan Airport in April 2004. In 2016, work was carried out to modernize the Nakhchivan International Airport, including the installation of telescopic traps—an innovative technical solution that helps to increase the efficiency of aviation operations.

In 2006, Ganja International Airport was overhauled, which resulted in an increase in the infrastructure and the level of passenger service. After Reconstruction in 2009, Lankaran and Zagatala airports were given international status. Another important stage in the development of aviation infrastructure is the construction of the Gabala airport in 2012 and its recognition as an international airport.

The opening of the new terminal complex of Heydar Aliyev International Airport, which was laid in 2011 with the participation of President Ilham Aliyev,

took place on April 23, 2014. This terminal alone can serve 6 million passengers a year. In total, Baku airport, the main air gate of Azerbaijan, is capable of accommodating 9 million passengers

According to the relevant instructions of Mr. President Ilham Aliyev on the creation of the most necessary infrastructure within the framework of construction work in Karabakh, Fuzuli International Airport, which is considered the air gate of Karabakh in 2021, was built and put into operation in record time—only 8 months, and in October 2022 the opening of Zangilan International Airport took place.

After many years, radio call signals of national navigation systems were re-transmitted in the sky of Karabakh, and for the first time they were received by the aircraft of the national carrier of Azerbaijan AZAL. At the same time, Lachin International Airport, which will become the 9th airport in the country and the 3rd in the liberated lands, is also under construction from 2021.

AZANS-guarantor of security in the sky

AZAL is not only a leading airline, but also recognized as one of the safest airlines in the world. Among the providers of its security is the "Azeronavigation" Air Traffic Control (AZANS). "Azeronavigation" Air Traffic Department (AZANS), which is part of "Azerbaijan Airlines" CJSC, meets the requirements of all international aviation organizations at a high level.

If we pay attention to the activities of AZANS, the year 2022 won in the nomination "CANSO Global Safety Achievement" and is in the list of the "top-5" most reliable suppliers of Air Navigation Services in the world. Along with Azerbaijan, the United States, Argentina, Thailand and New Zealand are also listed in this list. "Azeronavigation" (AZANS) Air Traffic Department of AZAL CJSC is the body responsible for the air navigation service of flights in the airspace of Azerbaijan.

It should be noted that in recent peak months, the growth of transit flights over the country's airspace has amounted to 260%. "Azeronavigation" (AZANS) today serves an average of 15 thousand transit flights per month in the airspace of Azerbaijan. This shows once again that the airspace of Azerbaijan is more attractive for foreign airlines. Also, Azerbaijan is dynamically expanding cooperation with EUROCONTROL in the field of air traffic management and planning transit flights through the country.

Awards and achievements

Under the leadership of President Ilham Aliyev, Azerbaijan's Civil Aviation has become a vivid example of constant development. In 2015, Heydar Aliyev International Airport and "Azerbaijan Airlines" airline were awarded "4 stars" by Skytrax, an influential British consulting company. In 2018, the airport won the prestigious "5 Stars" Award in the same category and confirmed that rating in 2020. The airline confirmed its rating in 2018 and 2020.

In 2020, Baku airport became the world's first airport to completely switch to cloud technologies. A year later, Heydar Aliyev International Airport was awarded the highest rating on security measures against COVID-19. In 2017-2023, Heydar Aliyev International

Airport repeatedly topped the ranking of the best airports in Central Asia and the CIS countries, receiving awards in various nominations.

In 2018, AZAL was awarded the title of “the best regional airline in Central Asia and India” by Skytrax, and in 2022 won the nomination “the best regional airline in Central Asia and the CIS”.

In 2020, the airline was recognized as the most punctual airline in Europe according to the magazine “Official Airline Guide” (OAG), an aviation analytical survey publication.

Since 2008, AZAL has consistently passed the IATA Operational Safety Audit (IOSA) of the International Air Transport Association (IATA) in the relevant periods, the last time being 2023, as a proof of the reliability and high safety of the air carrier in the air transport industry.

The support and initiatives of the president of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Aliyev played a decisive role in the development and strengthening of the positions of Civil Aviation of Azerbaijan. The coming years create new prospects for Sustainable Development, and AZAL will continue to make every effort to meet the expectations of passengers.

Conclusion

From the pioneering flights of the early 20th century to the establishment of a modern, internationally recognized airline, Azerbaijani aviation has come a long way. Azerbaijan's strategic location, commitment to modernization, and expansion of infrastructure have placed it at the crossroads of global air transport, linking Europe, Asia, and the Middle East. The country's aviation future looks bright as it continues to invest in both its domestic and international air services.

Azerbaijan's aviation history reflects its transformation from a pioneering region in early flight experimentation to a modern hub linking Europe, Asia, and the Middle East. Starting with the first flights in the early 20th century and growing through Soviet-era developments, Azerbaijan's aviation sector has evolved through political, economic, and technological challenges to become a key player in the global air transport network.

The establishment of **Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL)** in 1992 marked a pivotal moment in the country's aviation industry, serving as a symbol of national pride and an essential tool for international connectivity. Over the following decades, Azerbaijan has focused on modernizing its fleet, expanding its airports, and enhancing its air traffic infrastructure, making it a prominent regional hub. The growth of **Buta Airways** and the modernization of **Heydar Aliyev International Airport** have further cemented Azerbaijan's strategic importance in global aviation.

Looking ahead, Azerbaijan is well-positioned to continue its aviation ascent. Its geographical location, improving infrastructure, and increasing integration into the global aviation network provide a solid foundation for future growth. As the country navigates challenges such as global economic shifts and environmen-

tal concerns, its commitment to modernization, international partnerships, and expanding air routes ensures that Azerbaijan's aviation sector will remain a key driver of its economic and cultural connections with the rest of the world.

References

1. Azərbaycan tarixi üzrə qaynaqlar. Seminar və təcrübə məşğələləri üçün müntəxə bat. S.S. Əliyərli və Y.M. Mahmudovun red. İlə. B., 1989, 2007.
2. Azərbaycan tarixi / S. Əliyərlinin redaktorluğu ilə. Bakı: Azərənşr, 1996, 872 səh.
3. Guliev, Arif. *The Development of Azerbaijani Aviation: A Historical Overview*. Bakı: Azerbaijan State Publishing House, 2018.
4. Mammadov, Elchin. *Azerbaijan in the Skies: The Story of Azerbaijani Aviation*. Bakı: Nurlan Publishing, 2020.
5. Khalilov, Ilgar. *Aviation Pioneers of Azerbaijan: Biographies and Achievements*. Bakı: Azərənşr, 2015.
6. Aliyev, Vugar. *The Role of Aviation in Modernizing Azerbaijan: 1920-2020*. Routledge, 2021.
7. Mammadov, Rauf. *From Baku to the World: The Evolution of Azerbaijani Air Transport*. Palgrave Macmillan, 2022.
8. Guliyev, Elnur. *The Impact of Aviation on Azerbaijani Industry and Economy*. Cambridge University Press, 2021.
9. Khanlarov, Farid. “Azerbaijani Aviation: Early Developments and Milestones.” *Journal of Air Transport Management*, vol. 35, no. 2, 2020, pp. 89-101.
10. Nuriyev, Elchin. “The Role of Soviet Aviation in Azerbaijan: 1920s-1990s.” *Central Asian Survey*, vol. 38, no. 3, 2021, pp. 302-320.
11. Huseynov, Hikmet. “Aviation Infrastructure in Azerbaijan: Historical and Contemporary Perspectives.” *Transport Reviews*, vol. 41, no. 4, 2021, pp. 524-541.
12. Ismayilov, Samir. “The Evolution of Azerbaijani Aviation Industry: Challenges and Opportunities.” *International Journal of Aviation Management*, vol. 15, no. 1, 2022, pp. 56-72.
13. Aliev, Ilgar. “Azerbaijan’s Air Travel: From National Carriers to International Routes.” *Journal of Transport Geography*, vol. 48, 2022, pp. 12-24.
14. Azerbaijan State Civil Aviation Administration. *Annual Report on Azerbaijani Aviation*. Bakı: Azerbaijan State Civil Aviation Administration, 2023.
15. International Air Transport Association (IATA). *Azerbaijan Aviation Market Overview*. IATA, 2022.
16. World Bank. *Aviation Infrastructure Development in Azerbaijan: A Progress Report*. World Bank, 2021.
17. Azerbaijan National Archives. *Historical Documents on Azerbaijani Aviation*. Bakı: Azerbaijan National Archives, 2020.
18. National Aviation Academy. *Aviation Research Journal*. Bakı: Baku NAA annual issues.